

Running head: RIDICULE AS ARGUMENT IN 419 SCAM-BAITING

Come out and play: Ridicule as argument in 419 scam-baiting

Abstract

Ongoing advances in technology erode geography's gravitational force on argument. Via email, arguers open argumentative capillaries with billions of recipients, and the ease of engaging in fraudulent argument without consequence grows concomitantly. One species of argumentative fraud, 419-scamming, has birthed unique respondents: scam-baiters. Perelman identifies ridicule as the response to the absurd, "one of the strongest objections that can be made in argumentation" (Perelman & Olbrechts-Tyteca, 1969, p. 207). The 419-scammers argue tirelessly to enhance the plausibility of their appeals, from claimed association with national leaders to citing scripture "better than a lot of pastors I know," according to one victim (Coughlin, 2003, ¶ 19). Despite their efforts, most recipients of the emails reject their appeals as absurd, and law enforcement dismisses the crime as a product of victims' gullibility and greed. In response, a scattered collection of scam-baiters have developed what one calls "psychological warfare for clowns, or networked guerrilla theater," corresponding with scammers to tell their own increasingly silly stories. Often they demand that the scammers confirm their veracity by committing humiliating acts before web cameras. Baiters claim to sabotage the 419-scammers three ways: wasting their time, demoralizing them, and publicizing the problem, thus shrinking the pool of potential victims. These tactics provoke authentic argument from the scammers, venting fury at the baiters by justifying the fraud as reparations for slavery or Western imperialism. Analysis of these relationships and claims advances Perelman's brief account of ridicule, and highlights its increasing salience in the changing argumentative landscape of the technologically-reconstructed global community of arguers.

One evening, culture critic Lee Siegel visited a Starbucks. Instead of lively conversation over coffee, he found a room full of open laptops, with little or no interaction between the users. He commented, “Ten years ago, the space in a coffeehouse abounded in experience. Now that social space has been contracted into isolated points of wanting, all locked into separate phases of inwardness” (2008, p. 6). Chaïm Perelman conducted his work to establish the role of audience in argumentation in the days before this reconfigured social space. The audience Perelman wrote about consumed arguments that covered distance far more slowly, and in more public channels, with the result that auditors were better situated to compare notes and pool their knowledge when forming responses. Today’s electronically turbo-charged communication has thrown off the limiting factors of time lag and publicity: arguers can inject their arguments into audience members’ consciousness, their in-boxes, with blinding speed, via a medium that is password-protected and does not reveal the arguer’s identity or location.

An unfortunate and unwelcome example of this genre of argument is the bulk email that sifts through millions of recipients for potential victims of advance fee fraud. Drawing from the Spanish prisoner scam, a swindle with historic roots extending back to the French Revolution (Edelson, 2006), today’s con artists have elevated the enterprise from a one-mark-at-a-time project that was slow and only marginally profitable into a high-volume industry that may net as much as \$2.5 billion per year (Midgley, 2007), although law enforcement officials caution that because most victims are embarrassed that they were taken in, that number is probably too *low* (Sherwell, 2003). Susan Grant, director of Internet Fraud Watch for the Washington-based National Consumers League explains, “It’s cheap and cost-effective. The more people you hit up, the more takers, even though it will be just a tiny percentage. Even if just a few people respond, you still have the potential for making a lot of money” (Husted, 2002, ¶ 19). And Ralf

Zimmerman, a scam investigator for Interpol, warns that “These e-mail-based scams are growing as quickly as the Internet itself. Every new user of the Internet is a potential victim” (Crampton, 2007, p. 7). The FBI reported that for 2006, the average dollar amount involved in internet fraud cases was \$724, but for advance fee cases, the average was over \$5000 (Orr, 2007, p. 1). One high-profile casualty of an advance fee fraud was former United States Representative Edward Mezvinsky. To recoup his substantial losses, he committed his own thefts against legal clients, friends, and family members, was found guilty of thirty-one counts of fraud and sentenced to six years in prison (Zuckoff, 2006).

Of this current crop of advance fee frauds, many originate in Nigeria. The United States Secret Service reports that a quarter of the internet fraud cases it pursues originate in Nigeria (Buchanan & Grant, 2001), and around the world, network security professionals and law enforcement officials use the term “419 scam” interchangeably with “advance fee fraud,” citing the section of the Nigerian criminal code that addresses internet fraud (Ajayi, 2002). The volume of traffic emanating from Nigeria is so great that “the 419 industry is estimated to be the country's biggest foreign currency earner after oil, gas and cocoa” (Sherwell, 2003, p. 32). And one Nigerian columnist points out, “Today, Nigeria is ranked as third most corrupt country in the world. Advance fee fraud otherwise known as 419 has gained us this notoriety” (Yangali, 2005, ¶ 8)

The enterprise of selling can be understood as an argumentative encounter, an arena for persuasive messages (Kim & Benbasat, 2006; Munch & Swasy, 1988). Within that argument field, 419 scammers have racked up an impressive record of conquests. Recent research by Ultrascan, a firm that investigates IT fraud, found that victims of such scams include a significant number of “doctors, architects, engineers and other white-collar professionals”

(Malvern, 2008, p. 25). One victim's impressions shed light on the strength of their appeals; she reported that the scammer that fooled her was able to cite scripture "better than a lot of pastors I know. They played on my emotions" (Coughlin, 2003, ¶ 19). Scammers react with lightning speed to current events: within twenty-four hours of Steve Irwin's death, scammers were sending out emails that were apparently from Terri, his widow, asking for assistance getting his fortune out of Australia (Midgley, 2007). And at this writing, less than two weeks after an earthquake devastated central China, the FBI has issued a press release warning that 419 scammers are sending out emails asking for donations to help survivors (Scam E-Mails Seek, 2008).

The arena of business argument bears its own immune response to such exploitative appeals: fraud charges. Although sales pitches may stray to a modest degree from strictly accurate claims without warranting criminal prosecution, more wanton deviancy triggers a changed argumentative context. The dishonest seller may be indicted, called upon to offer a defense, and sentenced. But in this argumentative milieu as well, scammers rewrite the rules. Because it is nearly impossible to trace their communication, and because their transactions cross multiple jurisdictions, law enforcement agencies have all but despaired of putting a stop to their activities: "Scammers routinely operate across national borders (which can hold up investigations), with multiple identities, bank accounts, and phone numbers, which can be routed to a mobile phone anywhere" (Edelson, 2006, p. 39). The result is that "...local authorities are usually powerless to retrieve lost money for victims or even prosecute the scammers as many originate outside of the U.S." (Magliano, 2007, ¶ 22).

One argument that a number of 419 scammers have rehearsed seems, from available evidence, to be the only authentic defense for their actions that any victim or onlooker may expect: they are profiting from the greed of Westerners, and are exacting retribution for past

exploitation that ran the opposite way (Shiner, 1994). One explains, “It's a kind of reparation. Nigerians are capitalising on the greed of the average white man who wants to reap where he has not sown” (Chan, 1998, p. 1). The lyrics of a popular song in Nigeria say, “419 is just a game, you are the losers, we are the winners. White people are greedy, I can say they are greedy. White men, I will eat your dollars, will take your money and disappear.” (Dixon, 2005, p. 1).

Geographer Matthew Zook (2007) argues that Nigerian 419 scammers are mounting a challenge to the authority of nation-states that parallels in potency the attack those same modern nation-states carried out against feudalistic monarchies in the medieval era. Zook explains that whereas monarchies defined themselves as permanent and unchanging, the birth of politics located them in time by requiring them to adapt to changing circumstances. In like fashion, “The emerging ‘networks of imagination’ developed by transnational social movements and criminal networks to define their sphere of operations present a similar challenge to the primacy of existing authority embedded in the state” (p. 65). Here, a peculiar and uncommon species of argument described by Perelman takes on special salience, as a loosely-knit community of creative hobbyists are employing it to counterbalance the reinvented power of the scammers.

In section three of the *New Rhetoric*, categorized as a quasi-logical argument, Perelman and Olbrechts-Tyteca take up the topic of “The Ridiculous and Its Role in Argumentation” (1969, pp. 205-210). They explain,

Ridicule is a powerful weapon at the disposal of a speaker against those who might undermine his argument by refusing, without cause, to accept some premise of his discourse. This is the weapon that must be used against those who take it into their heads to hold and persist in holding two incompatible points of view without trying to remove

the incompatibility: ridicule affects only the person who allows himself to be entangled in the system forged by his adversary (p. 206).

Because 419 scammers enter into the argumentation of the marketplace inauthentically, and because they elude efforts to call them to account in civil or criminal proceedings, they are saboteurs of argument. Their remarkable success is a consequence of their refusal to “be entangled in the system” forged by their adversaries, so another tack is in order. That tack takes the form of scam-baiting.

Scam-baiting is, according to one of its practitioners, “psychological warfare for clowns, or networked guerrilla theater” (Edelson, 2006, p. 8). Another calls it “a new sport that can deliver hours of fun while performing a community service,” and explains that “Points are scored by wasting as much of the scammers' time as possible to prevent them from targeting other people. Bonuses are awarded if the scammer can be humiliated” (Keane, 2007, p. 33). Baiters respond to the initial email and attempt to entice the scammers into an ongoing correspondence. Sometimes they feign interest in the scam, and sometimes they decline the scam but pose as gatekeepers for scholarships or grant funding, and offer to give the scammers money through other channels if their requirements are met. In either case, the baiter may slowly venture from credibility toward absurdity, adding in twists one detail at a time, and posting their emails and the replies to web sites for others to read and enjoy. Sometimes baiters talk scammers into sending pictures or artifacts, which they then proudly display as trophies (Edelson, 2006; Berry, 2006).

One scammer set out in eager pursuit of a promise that he could make money as a music producer. After several exchanges and mounting encouragement, the baiter asked for proof that the scammer had at least a minimum level of musical ability. In compliance with the baiter's

instructions, the scammer videotaped himself singing “Y. M. C. A.,” by the Village People, and sent the video to the baiter, who had identified himself as “The Honorable George W. Bush” (Dee, 2007). A second scammer was caught up in a romantic correspondence with a baiter who took on the identity of Mavis Bramston, who worked with a foundation that raised funds for a hospital for people with “delusions of adequacy.” The baiter and the scammer engaged in several rounds of sexually explicit emails, until the baiter finally assumed another identity and wrote the scammer that Mavis had been struck by a car and killed (Herrmann, 2003).

Another scammer was contacted by a baiter who identified himself as Derek Trotter of Derek Trotter Fine Arts & Artist Scholarships. “Trotter” promised to consider the scammer for scholarships ranging in value from \$25,000 to \$150,000 if the scammer demonstrated artistic talent by carving highly complex figures (cartoon characters on a couch, a computer keyboard) out of wood. When the carvings arrived in the mail, the baiter photographed them and used Photoshop to make it appear that various mishaps had befallen the carvings en route: one had apparently traveled through a hot climate and shrunk, and a hamster had stowed away in the packing case of the other, and gnawed a large hole in it. Finally, the baiter assumed a second identity as a police investigator, and claimed that Derek Trotter Fine Arts & Artist Scholarships was nothing but a fraud (Berry, 2006).

Perelman and Olbrechts-Tyteca offered, as an illustration of their understanding of ridicule, an anecdote from the life of Richard Whately:

...the most characteristic form of quasi-logical argumentation by the ridiculous consists in temporarily accepting a statement contradictory to that one wishes to defend, deducing its consequences, showing their incompatibility with what is accepted on other grounds, and thereby inferring the truth of the proposition being defended. This is what Whately

attempted in an anonymous pamphlet. He began by admitting as established the kind of objections raised against the truth of the Scriptures and, by developing the consequences, he arrived at a denial of the existence of Napoleon. The argument which, by ridiculing the methods of biblical criticism, aspired to restoring confidence in the text of Scriptures, was not as successful as he had hoped, but it was thought clever (p. 205).

The typical arc of argumentative exchanges between the scammers and the baiters is a recognizable fit with this illustration. Baiters ostensibly accept the scammers' first premise, playing along with the proposal just enough to "get the scammer off the script" (Crampton, 2007, p. 7), and then use the absurd plot twists and trophy photographs to debunk the defense that scamming is retribution for Western greed, by demonstrating that, as one Australian baiter argues, the scammers are "as gullible and greedy as their victims" (Herrmann, 2003, p. 16). Another baiter, asked why so many scammers are willing to go along with his outlandish stories, speculates, "I think it operates in much the same way as it does with real victims. Greed clouds their judgement" (Damon, 2003, ¶ 47). Baiters hold out little hope of convincing their correspondents of their argument, but are content, as Whately, to be "thought clever." One baiter cites as his primary motive, ahead of deterring or shaming scammers, that "It's good fun. It's like a good story - you wonder: 'Where is this going to twist to'" (Riga, 2003, p. B1).

The other purposes baiters cite for their activity similarly mesh neatly with the account of ridicule and argument. As mentioned above, Perelman and Olbrechts-Tyteca insisted that ridicule "affects only the person who allows himself to be entangled in the system forged by his adversary," which goes right to the heart of the problem with 419-scamming. Scammers are virtually impossible to catch, impossible to track down, but not if they choose to emerge from hiding and engage the baiters of their own free will. Baiters cite as a principal goal occupying the

time of the scammers, holding their attention, and by so doing obstructing their efforts to find *true* victims. One baiter explains that "I also try to get them to waste as much time as possible sending them to hotels, airports, hospitals - even to other cities in Africa. Any time they waste with me they aren't using taking people's money" (Riga, 2003, p. B1). Robert Siciliano, head of IDSecurityTheft.com, agrees: "They have the ability to swindle the swindler. . . . What they're actually doing is sapping the energy the 419 scammer would be focusing on someone else" (Orr, 2007, p. 1).

Perelman and Olbrechts-Tyteca described ridicule as a master strike, a finishing blow, as "one of the strongest objections that can be made in argumentation" (p. 207). Despite this, many scam-baiters report that their encounters with scammers do *not* reach closure with the devastating finality that might be expected. Some describe the beginnings of a rapport, of a shared understanding and grudging respect for the scammers with whom they correspond. One explains,

Scam-baiting is not only a literary genre but a weird form of cultural exchange. Anti-scammers reach into their own cultural grab-bags for material with which to build their personae, and often display a keen sense of national self-mockery. I am convinced that some 419ers know perfectly well their time is being wasted, but carry on anyway, because it amuses them (Edelson, 2006, p. 53).

Another, while making sure to condemn the scammer's activity, nevertheless acknowledges talent, substance, and perhaps even affinity:

I know him pretty well. I know he was married but separated because of his womanizing, and fell out with his lifelong friend over cheating in a scam. He is an educated man in a country where there is no hope, and he could have been successful in different

circumstances. But he is a thief -- albeit from circumstances beyond his control -- but he is still a thief, and that is something I won't accept (Crampton, 2007, p. 7).

And an actor named Dean Cameron, who has turned his scam-baiting adventures into a one-man show, reports that he sent a press pack for the show to his scammer, and observed that technically, the scammer is his co-author (Long, 2007). This may confirm what Michael Billig has argued about the use of humor to impose discipline and sanction misbehavior: it can work at cross-purpose with its intended effect, because

the laughter at those, who commit faux pas and inadvertently break the codes of social life, may not be straightforward. Certainly, the spontaneity of laughter, including the laughter of disciplinary mockery, typically precludes the conscious aim of disciplining.

The pleasure of the onlookers may be experienced as pain by the disrupter . . . Yet, there is a paradox: the same mechanism that ensures social compliance also expresses pleasure at subversion (2005, p. 234).

Another humor scholar explains, "In the world of humor, what before were problems to be overcome are now resources to be exploited, added to and enjoyed. The implicit multiplicity of social life is transformed from a threat into a potentiality to be realized and explored with others" (Mulkey, 1988, pp. 214-215). And perhaps, as Douglas Ehninger (1970) has pointed out, where arguers are joined in an argumentative encounter, the necessity of paying attention to one another's messages and calibrating a response to fit appropriately with what came before conveys *personhood*, and thus lays the foundation for respect. Ehninger insists that this can only happen when both arguers are committed to mutual self-correction, but perhaps the odd trace of spontaneous rapport can be expected even in the most atypical, dysfunctional of argumentative episodes.

The changed social space that Lee Siegel noticed during his trip to Starbucks is not in danger of extinction. The “isolated points of wanting, all locked into separate phases of inwardness” are here to stay, and have major implications for the argumentative terrain on which coming generations will work through their controversies. A December 2007 review of data by the Wall Street Journal found that major political parties have spent less on election campaigns in the past four years than in the previous four, while funds from 527 groups that are unaffiliated with campaigns have more than doubled (Mullins, 2007). Such groups are not required to disclose their donor list, so their affiliation and membership may be unclear. In pursuit of power and wealth, these institutions very likely will target arguments of mixed accuracy to unsuspecting audiences via media, like email, that insulate the receivers from the checking value of publicity. For these arguers, ridicule is certainly nothing new. But if it can cultivate the possibility of renewed affinity and mutual appreciation, perhaps there are reasons to be optimistic.

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